

Interpretable and Adjustable Definitions of AI Fairness using Fuzzy Logic

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Abstract

The ubiquitous adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in everyday life has created concerns over harmful biases it may perpetuate or create. Devising numerical fairness definitions and approximately satisfying them has been the subject of intensive research, but this process often relies on arbitrarily choosing how tight the approximation should be and which properties it safeguards. We address this lack of transparency by setting up Basic fuzzy Logic (BL) as an interpretable representation that admits continuous-valued mathematical counterparts. By modeling common assumptions in this logic, we create a framework where one can extract the underlying BL motivation of existing fairness definitions, so that their choices can be reinterpreted in new application contexts. We demonstrate how to engage stakeholders to suggest fairness assessment criteria for factual AI systems while incorporating their opinions. Experiments on three public datasets show that context-specific choices—such as thresholds and logic type—alter which models are judged as fair.

1 Introduction

As AI systems tend to replicate and exacerbate real-world discrimination, making them fair is a subject of intensive research (Ntoutsi et al. 2020; Barocas, Hardt, and Narayanan 2023; Mitchell et al. 2021; Mehrabi et al. 2021). Fairness definitions depend on the social context, such as the geographic area, local history, and culture where systems are deployed. They also depend on the stakeholders evaluating the systems (John-Mathews, Cardon, and Balagué 2022; Li et al. 2023; Mielke et al. 2016; Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Russell 2021), such as policymakers, business owners, or affected vulnerable groups. In practice, those definitions echo philosophical statements (Binns 2018) and quantify disparities between demographic groups like genders (men vs women, etc.) and ethnicities (Caucasian vs African vs Asian, etc.).

Unfortunately, fairness definitions and their parameters are often applied with arbitrary criteria, thus promoting “corrections” that are irrelevant or downright harmful. Take, for example, a binary classifier that exhibits *disparate mistreatment* between men and women by yielding different false positive rates between them (Zafar et al. 2017). Equalizing the rates may require predictive performance concessions, so it is common for research and libraries to allow relative rate

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differences up to 20%.¹ However, this threshold originates from guidelines addressing the *different problem and -often-context* of *disparate impact* between men and women (Biddle 2017), for which the relative difference is instead computed between the positive rates of the genders. The threshold’s usage is thus unjustified for disparate mistreatment, or the protection of other attributes or more genders.

In this work we seek a transparent link between numerical fairness definitions and the opinions of people proposing them. For example, it should be understood which concept corresponds to the 20% threshold above. This way, definitions can be audited and adjusted to reflect the opinions of new stakeholders when the application context changes, for example when updating the quantitative parts of AI regulation or adapting them from other countries.

We employ Basic Fuzzy Logic (BL) as an interpretable representation that models continuous values in the range $[0, 1]$. In this logic, we infer an expression for worst-case bias given common assumptions, as well as how free hypotheses supplied by domain experts—we call those hypotheses *restrictions*—can be injected as requisites for bias. Figure 1 exemplifies an adjustment of context choices by converting mathematical fairness criteria to equivalent restrictions and conversely.

Figure 1: Adjusting definitions in new contexts. Highlighted values correspond to the truth value that small numerical deviations are allowed, which may change.

Our work not only interprets existing fairness criteria but

¹As a testament to its widespread adoption, the 20% threshold is recommended by the online application of the Aequitas (Saleiro et al. 2018) framework (<http://aequitas.dssg.io/upload.html>).

also supports the creation of new ones. By making assumptions explicit, we enable adjustment of what is considered fair to the application context. Practical usage is demonstrated in creating definitions for two real systems through interdisciplinary collaboration that incorporates stakeholder opinions. Finally, experiments on three public datasets show that choices, such as those derived from the opinions, matter.

Our contribution is threefold:

- a. We establish a BL framework where abstract fairness definitions are proposed by domain experts in the form of restrictions over worst-cases biases. Gathering stakeholder opinions lets the logic’s evaluation mechanism generate measures of fairness in each application context.
- b. We match existing practices like thresholding to BL counterparts that explain context-specific choices. We also show how to, given ad-hoc mathematical formulas, reverse engineer bias restrictions in the logic.
- c. We demonstrate practical usage, and that choices delegated to stakeholders span a wide variety of evaluations.

2 Background

Quantifying group fairness

Defining and imposing fairness on AI is the subject of ongoing debate that includes many types of mathematical and procedural evaluation, like the EU’s AI Act and Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (Ala-Pietilä et al. 2020), and NIST’s AI Risk Management Framework (AI 2023). One course of action is to mitigate discrimination according to mathematical definitions (Ntoutsis et al. 2020; Barocas, Hardt, and Narayanan 2023; Mitchell et al. 2021; Mehrabi et al. 2021) that are broadly categorized into i) group fairness that focuses on equal treatment between population groups or subgroups, and ii) individual fairness that focuses on fair treatment of individuals, for example by yielding similar predictions for similar features (Dwork et al. 2012). Measures of discrimination often quantify the numerical deviation from exact definitions, and are either minimized or set as constraints (Xinying Chen and Hooker 2023).

Here we present common measures for assessing the group fairness of classifiers (Castelnovo et al. 2021), where analogous measures port the same principles to other predictive tasks (Li et al. 2023; Xinying Chen and Hooker 2023). First, $prule = \frac{\min pr}{\max pr}$ (Biddle 2017) and Calders-Verwer disparity (Calders and Verwer 2010) quantify disparate impact, that is, deviations from positive rate (pr) equality between predictions for two groups of samples S and S' . Disparate mistreatment (Zafar et al. 2017) captures (mis)classification differences between the groups as:

$$|\Delta m| = |m(S) - m(S')|$$

where m is a measure over a group of samples, such as their false positive rates (fpr) or false negative rates (fnr). The same formula expresses Calders-Verwer disparity when applied to pr . It is thus a prospective building block of generalized fairness evaluation (Roy, Horstmann, and Ntoutsis 2023; Krasanakis and Papadopoulos 2024). For true positive rates (tpr), small $|\Delta tpr|$ is known as equal opportunity (Hardt,

Price, and Srebro 2016), and equalized odds refer to also obtaining small $|\Delta tnr|$ for true negative rates (tnr).

Fairness concerns may span multiple protected attributes (e.g., genders, races). Differential fairness computes the maximum of $df = 1 - prule$ across all pairs of demographic intersections (Foulds et al. 2020). Furthermore, multiple biases may be combined, such as in $|\Delta fpr| + |\Delta fnr|$ (Krasanakis et al. 2018). Multiple concerns could be contradictory (Kleinberg, Mullainathan, and Raghavan 2016), but still reduced to one number (Hooker and Williams 2012; Roy, Horstmann, and Ntoutsis 2023) through a maximum, minimum, or weighted average. They can also model individual fairness (Dwork et al. 2012; Kim et al. 2019) by setting each individual as a separate group.

Related work

Seeking interpretable fairness definitions, statistical tests indicate discrimination (Watkins, McKenna, and Chen 2022) when rejecting the null hypothesis that group distributions (instead of aggregate quantities) are indistinguishable. But they arbitrarily decide when results are significant; p-values now serve as alternative measures of discrimination. Counterfactual fairness (Kusner et al. 2017; Carey and Wu 2022) employs causal models to make predictions in a would-be fair reality,² but relies on approximate true world models. Recent variations suggest sequences of human actions needed to overcome discrimination (Karimi, Schölkopf, and Valera 2021; Verma et al. 2020; De Toni et al. 2022); our work could help quantify the fairness of those actions.

Fairness has also been transcribed from abstract statements to unambiguous propositional logic (Ignatiev et al. 2018, 2020; Belle 2023; Lee et al. 2023). Such transcriptions cannot be relaxed into measures of discrimination because they coarsen continuous-valued intermediate assessments to binary truth values. To allow optimization, they may impose *exactly zero* discrimination while maximizing accuracy, but the accuracy cost can be so extreme compared to numeric relaxation that it renders systems unusable. In terms of axiomatizing fairness uncertainty, initial links between Rawl’s difference principle (Ashrafiyan 2023) and the logical system of Gödel fuzzy logic have been identified (Suzuki 2018).

Fuzziness has encoded fairness uncertainty for datasets (Nápoles and Koumeri 2022), opinion evaluation (Chen, Hsieh, and Do 2015), and belief merging (Konieczny and Pérez 2002). The first case quantifies the leading role of attributes in decision processes; ad-hoc measures like this serve as starting points of our approach. Opinion evaluation overcomes single-valued uncertainty with usage of fuzzy numbers instead of one truth value. This is orthogonal to combining all statements in one reusable formula, and is a promising extension of this work. Belief merging combines different truth values of beliefs, and has been used on the same class of t-norm logics that we explore (Viana and Alcântara 2017), but it has not been applied on supporting end-to-end logic reasoning about fairness definitions.

²Rosenblatt and Witter (2023) observe that counterfactual fairness is a type of group fairness.

Fuzziness is used in other domains to create reusable “white box” models based on expert modeling (Sugeno and Yasukawa 1993; Voinov et al. 2016), so that qualitative opinions can fill details (e.g., (Wieland and Gutzler 2014; Fulton et al. 2015; Dambacher et al. 2009)). We also gather opinions for logic terms that would normally be binary and, in the linguistic front, suggest leaving statements intentionally vague to empower stakeholders by letting them affect how the modeling is interpreted. We also enable reasoning in logics other than the traditional Gödel logic.

Basic fuzzy logic

Fuzzy logic reasons over uncertain facts by endowing statements X with truth values in the unit interval $\mu(X) \in [0, 1]$ (Zadeh 1978). Monoidal T-norm based Logics (MTLs) (Esteva and Godo 2001; Dubois and Prade 2004; Spada and Di Nola 2008; Cintula, Fermüller, and Noguera 2023) axiomatize how to evaluate the truth values of logic expressions given truth values of statements and connectives like conjunction $\&$ and implication \rightarrow . In particular, left-continuous operators \star called *t-norms* evaluate the truth value of conjunction, that is, of two expressions being true simultaneously, given that: $x \star 0 = 0$, $x \star 1 = x$, $x \star y = y \star x$, $(x \star y) \star z = x \star (y \star z)$, if $x \leq y$ then $(x \star z) \leq (y \star z)$.

T-norms admit a *residuum* operator \Rightarrow modeling the truth value of implication per $(x \star y) \leq z \triangleq x \leq (y \Rightarrow z)$, where \triangleq is equality by definition and has lowest priority. We write:

$$\mu(X \& Y) \triangleq \mu(X) \star \mu(Y)$$

$$\mu(X \rightarrow Y) \triangleq \mu(X) \Rightarrow \mu(Y)$$

Each MTL contains strong (str) negation of expressions that corresponds to mutual exclusiveness. But logics also allow internal definition of weak (wk) negation that models set complements/antithetical statements that could hold simultaneously to an extent. For expressions X , and *False* the logic’s fallacy with $\mu(\text{False}) = 0$, negations are defined as:

$$\overset{\text{str}}{\neg} X \triangleq X \rightarrow \text{False}$$

$$\mu(\overset{\text{wk}}{\neg} X) \triangleq 1 - \mu(X)$$

Basic fuzzy Logic (BL) (Hájek 1998; Cignoli et al. 2000) is a class of MTLs that share a set of axioms corresponding to continuous (as opposed to left-continuous) t-norms. BL subclasses refer to logics that adopt specific t-norms to create an evaluation mechanism for truth values; they differ on numerical details but do not violate the common axioms. That is, *properties proven in BL hold for all of its subclasses*. One such property is that $x \star (x \rightarrow y) \triangleq \min\{x, y\}$.

3 BL Framework for Fairness Definitions

Modeling common assumptions

We make statements about bias *Bias* and fairness *Fair* depend on two others that could change while AI systems are created or deployed in the evolving reality: *discrimination E* set as a generic property that holds over some system or set of predictions, and *group membership S* for a specific group of people, for example to be protected. Exact interpretation

of these abstract statements is left for when BL definitions are adjusted to application contexts. As an example, group membership could reflect that predictions affect a group’s member, where groups range from all people belonging to a demographic to an individual (group of one person).

We derive discrimination from simpler concepts, namely the *indistinguishability* between predicate M reflecting that some property holds true for group members, and predicate M' that the same property holds true for a compared group, such as other groups, non-group members, or the total population. We set imbalance *Imb* as a common denominator of discrimination and group membership.

Propositions [a–c] below contain all terms. Fairness is considered mutually exclusive to (strong negation of) bias. Discrimination is the conceptual opposite (weak negation) of distinguishing between groups based on some property. Alternatives can be valid as well, but this modeling ends up replicating existing practices, so we consider it to capture commonly held domain knowledge.

- Imb* should logically imply discrimination, and be defined as an implication from group membership to some property. If no group members are encountered, imbalance can have any truth value in $[0, 1]$.
- Bias* is imbalance coexisting with group membership. *Fair* is mutually exclusive to that bias.
- E* is the opposite of M and M' implying each other.

Theoretical analysis

We transcribe the above textual statements to formal BL expressions below. Our goal is to afterwards apply logic rules to obtain truth values for the expressions (weak negation is not covered by BL inference, which is why *E* and not M is in the cornerstone of our analysis). This creates numerical formulas in which t-norms \star and residua \Rightarrow are known and determined by the choice of BL subclass. For brevity, we annotate the truth values of terms with a lower case of their name. For example, $e = \mu(E)$ and $s = \mu(S)$.

$\begin{aligned} \text{Imb is an implication from } S \text{ to some property} \\ \text{Imb} \rightarrow E \text{ for } \mu(S) \neq 0 \\ \text{Bias} \triangleq S \& \text{Imb} \\ \text{Fair} \triangleq \overset{\text{str}}{\neg} \text{Bias} \\ E \triangleq \overset{\text{wk}}{\neg} (M \leftrightarrow M') \text{ where } X \leftrightarrow Y \triangleq (X \rightarrow Y) \& (Y \rightarrow X) \end{aligned}$

Theorem 1. Any truth value function $g(s, e)$ admits bias s.t.

$$\text{bias} = s \star e \star g(s, e)$$

Any bias function also admits at least one such $g(s, e)$.

Proof. When $s = 0$ we get $\text{bias} = 0 \star \text{imb} = 0$. Otherwise, by definition $\mu(\text{Imb}) \Rightarrow e$ means that $\mu(\text{Imb}) \leq e$. As t-norms are non-decreasing, $\text{bias} = s \star \mu(\text{Imb}) \leq s \star e$. As t-norms in BL are continuous there also exists value $g(s, e) \in [0, 1]$ such that, for any bias that is a function of s, e :

$$s \star e \star 0 = 0 \leq \text{bias} \leq s \star e = s \star e \star 1$$

it holds that $bias = s \star e \star g(s, e)$. We implicitly allow extension of the logic with functions like weak negation that, if needed, can help us reproduce any function.

To show that any truth value function $g : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ yields a bias, we similarly rewrite $\mu(Imb) = e \star g(s, e)$ for at least one such function given a definition of imbalance. But there also exists a definition of imbalance as the truth value of the BL expression $e \star g(s, e)$ for any $g(s, e)$. Thus:

$$\{imb | imb(s, e) \leq e\} \equiv \{e \star g(s, e) | g : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]\}$$

where \equiv is the set equality operator. Therefore:

$$\{bias | Bias = S \& Imb\} \equiv \{s \star e \star g | g : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]\} \quad \square$$

Based on the theorem, the worst-case bias is given by $s \star e$, which implies that certain logics require zero discrimination to achieve fairness. Since this requirement is often impractical, one may instead prefer more relaxed, non-worst-case bias definitions. In this spirit, the theorem shows that any $bias$ function bounded above by $s \star e$ admits a corresponding BL statement G such that $\mu(G(S, E)) = g(s, e)$, allowing bias to be written in the same structured form. This existence is what allows us to reverse engineer the statement from any formula below. For example, we later deconstruct disparate impact mitigation from $prule \geq 0.8$ into a BL expression.

We refer to G as a *restriction*, since it is used to (partially) underestimate bias in certain cases. Restrictions may also include constant statements, that is, statements independent of group membership. Crucially, any BL statement can serve as a restriction, giving domain experts the flexibility to encode abstract fairness intuition in the framework. Finally, the theorem shows that $bias$ decreases as group membership decreases. This aligns with intuition of ignoring absent groups, such as a hypothetical demographic of unicorns. Whether fewer but non-zero group members are less important depends on the interpretation of S in practice. For instance, later experiments set $s = 1$ for all groups, regardless of size.

How to apply this framework

Practical application should start from a BL definition of fairness by either transcribing intuitive concerns to the logic, or reverse engineering them from mathematical counterparts or desired properties. This preliminary step requires a certain degree of logic proficiency or mathematical agility. Below is a concrete workflow for the reverse engineering process.

1. Identify an appropriate BL subclass (see next paragraph).
2. Select conditions that $bias \leq s \star e$ should satisfy.
3. Symbolically define function $g(s, e) \in [0, 1]$ so that $s \star e \star g(s, e)$ satisfies those conditions.
4. Write $g(s, e)$ using only constants independent of groups, s , e , \star and \Rightarrow . Then substitute the BL operators with equivalent connectives, and constants with statements. Also provide an abstract description for those statements.

The result is a restriction -with an equivalent BL definition- that captures domain knowledge but not choices of the application context; it contains neither numeric constants nor operations like relative or absolute errors. Adjusting the definition to new contexts is straightforward, though collaboration with social scientists is needed to gather people's choices:

1. Stakeholders choose a BL subclass (see next).
2. Stakeholders agree what the abstract descriptions of statements mean, and choose truth values for them. The choice can range from setting exact values to choosing how to compute those values.
3. Write down $bias = s \star e \star g(s, e)$. For example, given $G(s, e) = \overset{wk}{\rightarrow} E$ and choices $s = 0.5$ and $e = |\Delta pr|$, write $bias = s \star e \star (1 - e) = 0.5 \star |\Delta pr| \star (1 - |\Delta pr|)$ under the logic subclass. If there are more than two groups, combine biases as we show at the end of this section.

Measure comparison = BL subclass

Different fairness contexts require different assumptions about how bias restrictions, discrimination, and group membership are combined. In our framework, this choice is affected by selecting a BL subclass, which defines how logical conjunction ($\&$) and implication (\rightarrow) behave. We ground the subclass choice on the Mostert-Shields theorem (kle 2013), which states that all continuous t-norms are locally isomorphic to the three base types of Table 1. Intuitively:

Gödel logic. If there is any suspicion that the AI system discriminates against one or more groups, it should be considered unfair.

Product logic. As more discrimination issues arise, my trust in the AI system decreases. However, unless discrimination is absolutely certain, we hold onto a small possibility that the system might be fair.

Lukasiewicz logic. As more discrimination issues arise, my trust in the AI system decreases. At a certain point, we consider the system completely unfair, even if no single issue is definitively proven.

To understand differences between these logics, two statements with truth values 0.5 and 0.1 simultaneously hold true with truth values 0.1, 0.05, and 0, respectively. Mathematically, if all truth values $x \notin \{0, 1\}$ are nilpotent, i.e., satisfy $x \star x \star \dots \star x = 0$ for some number of conjunctions, t-norms are isomorphic to Lukasiewicz logic. This has the same strong and weak negation, and it fully models propositional logic (Chang 1959). Otherwise, if t-norms are idempotent, i.e., $x \star x = x$, they are isomorphic to Gödel logic, which avoids degradation of truth values given many partially true statements. Finally, t-norms that do not exhibit the above two properties for every $x \in [0, 1]$ are isomorphic to Product logic, which can model probability theory (Hájek, Godo, and Esteva 2013; Flaminio, Godo, and Ugolini 2018; Yurchenko 2021). Other logics could be considered too.

Table 1 also maps mathematical expressions for discrimination to logics. First, absolute differences $|\Delta m| = |m - m'|$ are the truth value of discrimination under Lukasiewicz logic. This is the only one of the three that justifies the practice of thresholding discrimination with no additional assumptions. For example, the discrimination threshold to achieve fairness in the worst case is the truth value $\mu(\overset{str}{\rightarrow} S)$ of *not* encountering group members:

$$fair = 1 \text{ only if } 0 = e \star s = \max\{e + s - 1, 0\}$$

Logic	T-norm	Implication	e (our definition)
Gödel	$x \star y \triangleq \min\{x, y\}$	$x \Rightarrow y \triangleq \{1 \text{ if } x \leq y, y \text{ otherwise}\}$	$1 - \min\{m, m'\}$
Product	$x \star y \triangleq x \cdot y$	$x \Rightarrow y \triangleq \{1 \text{ if } x \leq y, \frac{y}{x} \text{ otherwise}\}$	$1 - \frac{\min\{m, m'\}}{\max\{m, m'\}}$ (0 if $m = m' = 0$)
Lukasiewicz	$x \star y \triangleq \max\{x + y - 1, 0\}$	$x \Rightarrow y \triangleq \min\{1, 1 - x + y\}$	$ m - m' $

Table 1: The three base BL subclasses of the Mostert-Shields theorem, and resulting discrimination $e = \mu(E)$.

This is achieved when $e \leq 1 - s = \mu(\overset{str}{\neg} S)$.

Ratio comparisons fall under Product logic, where bias thresholds do not arise in the worst case but only when some implication is contained in the restriction. Without an implication, this logic can never reach zero truth value for bias given non-zero truth values for discrimination and group membership. This finding aligns with differential fairness already recognizes the need for more conservative definitions of bias (Foulds et al. 2020).

Finally, setting discrimination as the worst value is a definition that arises from Gödel logic. For example, when only two genders are considered, one minus the worst accuracy between men and women is a measure of discrimination. Under Gödel logic, worst case fairness can be achieved for $s > 0$ only for perfect values $m = m' = 1$.

Multiple fairness concerns = conjunction

More than one groups or group intersections (Foulds et al. 2020) could be protected. Concerns like these follow a scheme of quantifying discrimination between group pairs or between each group and the total population. They then employ aggregation mechanisms that reduce results to one assessment of bias or fairness (Roy, Horstmann, and Ntoutsis 2023). In settings with multiple multi-value sensitive attributes, each value of each attribute (or of each attribute intersection) becomes a separate group.

Let $i = 1, \dots, n$ be groups or intersections thereof (these could be overlapping), each stapled with its own fairness definition. Identifiers i may correspond to group pairs too. Furthermore, each group may have a different properties M_i and M'_i to be indistinguishable. We aim to aggregate fairness definitions that are the strong negation of biases $Bias_i$. In logic terms, imposing fairness for all i translates to a conjunction of all considered fairness definitions. In logic terms:

$$Fair \triangleq \&_i \overset{str}{\neg} Bias_i$$

AI creators should maximize the resulting truth values of fairness, for example through machine learning. In Product and Gödel logics, that value is binary with truth values 0 or 1 as a de facto numerical property of strong negation, and $bias$ could be mitigated instead. Above, $Fair \rightarrow \overset{str}{\neg} \&_i Bias_i$ but not necessarily the inverse; aggregating biases for optimization may not yield fairness for all groups. One generic option is to optimize for the worst value across biases (Roy, Iosifidis, and Ntoutsis 2022); this covers any logic, because all t-norms satisfy $\min\{x, y\} \leq x \star y$, and thus:

$$fair = \star_i (bias_i \Rightarrow 0) \geq \min_i (bias_i \Rightarrow 0)$$

so perfect fairness is achieved if $\min_i bias_i = 0$. This condition is strict in Gödel logic only; others can admit easier to

optimize conditions that still yield fairness. We leave these to case-by-case future investigation, which could also aggregate biases before strong negation.

4 Case Study

Application context and restriction

The above framework was applied in the MAMMMOth project to incorporate stakeholder opinions in assessing the fairness of two systems: one predicting bank loan approvals, and one performing identity verification by matching user pictures to identity document pictures. In the project, we worked with social scientists and vulnerable group communities who engaged actual people in local languages. This interdisciplinary effort also included stakeholder training, and we expect a similar mesh of expertise to be needed by others applying our framework. Organization details and employed social science methods lie outside the scope of this work, as we focus on the BL core and feedback processing.

Working with social scientists, we adopted the following question that they could discuss with laypeople but which we could theoretically leverage:

Q: Implementing actions to mitigate discrimination often comes at the direct cost of the AI system making more mistakes (e.g., failing to identify who is able to pay a loan back or to identify impostors in face verification). If you could choose, would you prioritize non-discrimination or correctness?

We created a restriction that a) satisfies fairness for some non-perfect assessment, b) accommodates the concept of correctness mentioned above, which we map to desired benefits by business owners, and c) incorporates values obtained for the above statement from a questionnaire with integer scales 1 – 5 ranging from *fully disagree* to *fully agree*.

If bias mitigation ends up more favored than performance, we opted for the restriction $\overset{strwk}{\neg} (Tol \rightarrow (Err \rightarrow E))$ where Err represents a loss of business benefits and Tol is a bias intolerance predicate obtained from above per:

$$\mu(Tol) = \max\{0, 1 - \frac{avg(Q)-1}{2}\}$$

where avg is the average among replies. If everyone selects full intolerance for bias, this formula assumes truth value 1, whereas from the halfway mark there would be no intolerance. The $\overset{strwk}{\neg}$ chain can be interpreted as *do not disagree*. In the absence of legislative requirements domain expertise drove the restriction’s design, with details provided in the appendix. Alternatives could also be valid, but *easy critique and auditing is possible precisely because our framework is transparent*.

Definitions from feedback

Circulating a questionnaire, we gathered feedback from 48 stakeholders that yielded the degree s of protecting each demographic, $\mu(Tol) = 0.06$, and Gödel as the preferred logic from the last section’s options. In that logic, $s \neq 0$ affect only the degree of bias but not perfect fairness satisfaction.

The questionnaire also led to the selection of $m = tpr$ for loan approval as the most important measure to safeguard among groups. Options included pr , tpr , tnr , and accuracy (acc) across groups, where measures were limited in number to reduce cognitive load and transcribed to laypeople-friendly terms matching the system being evaluated. For example, tpr for loan approval was translated to *Ensuring that those who are truly eligible for a loan get approved*.

Finally, system owners revealed the loss of business benefits as $\mu(E) = 1 - acc$ for loan approval. Substituting these choices to the BL framework under our restriction yields that perfect fairness ($fair = 1$) is satisfied only when

$$\min\{0.94, acc\} < \min_i tpr \leq \max\{0.94, acc\}$$

for loan approval across all groups i . The same process was followed for face verification, with only differences in results being that stakeholders designated all of tpr , tnr , acc as important, and system owners selected $\mu(E) = 1 - tnr$. We thus similarly obtain

$$\min\{0.94, tnr\} < \min_{m \in \{tpr, tnr, acc\}, i} m \leq \max\{0.94, tnr\}$$

Find related computations and simple statistical analysis that processes stakeholder replies in the appendix. We end up considering fairness only if at least one group underperforms; the definition prevents its own usage as unfair when other measures exceed both 94% and business benefits for all groups. Per-group tnr must also exceed 0.94 to allow $\min\{0.94, tnr\} < \min_i tnr$.

5 Experiments on the Impact of Choices

Setup and evaluation methodology

We investigate whether stakeholder choices are meaningful when evaluating machine learning systems on real data. *Our goal is not to optimize for fairness or accuracy, but to check whether fairness assessments vary substantially across context-dependent choices.*

To this end, we create 100 multilayer perceptron architectures with uniformly random $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ hidden layers of uniformly random $\{32, 64, 128\}$ dimensions each. We train those on optimizing accuracy and approximately achieving the previous section’s $\min_i(bias_i \Rightarrow 0)$ for a BL definition of one constant expression across three datasets, the three base logics, and five truth values for the constant.

We train architectures in each of the $3 \times 5 = 15$ numerical variations of each BL definition, and evaluate them in the same set of definitions, independently of training. This yields a combination of $15 \times 15 = 165$ train-test definitions. For each of those, we compute the proportion of the models that achieve perfect fairness on the test set ($fair = 1$). If stakeholder choices matter for training and testing, we would obtain high variance across outcomes. We thus track

both the variance and -to get a sense of whether it is large or small- the average of assessments for each dataset and each BL definition. The experimental methodology is presented in Figure 2. We train $165 \times 3 \times 100 = 49,500$ models.

Figure 2: Computing a standard deviation per BL definition and dataset that summarizes the impact of choices.

Training and hyperparameters

Model training employs binary cross entropy loss for accuracy optimization and performs in-processing bias mitigation (Wan et al. 2023) by adding a regularization term $\lambda \max_i bias_i$. This becomes zero only if $bias_i = 0$ for all groups i and we set a gradually increasing yet saturating weight $\lambda = 100 \cdot (1 - 0.99^{epoch})$ so that bias mitigation does not impact early epochs but dominates the latest stages of training (obtains learning rate $\in [0.95, 1)$). No early stopping or hyperparameter tuning takes place because our goal is not to find the best-performing system, but to see whether choices that depend on the context (the choice of logic subclass and the definition’s parameters) affect *the evaluation*.

Training runs for 300 epochs with no batches while using the Adam optimizer with 0.01 learning rate, 0.0005 weight decay, and default other parameters. These settings were chosen prior to experimentation and are common for datasets with a few thousand entries. Models are implemented in PyTorch 2.7.1 (Paszke et al. 2019), and fairness assessments carried out using FairBench 0.8.1 (Krasanakis and Papadopoulos 2024). Datasets are loaded with Pandas 2.3.1. All experiments run on a 24-core 2.2GHz CPU without GPU acceleration, and require less than 1GB of RAM.

Bias definitions are used directly in the training loss without any relaxation, as their logic-based truth values derived from our framework are differentiable almost everywhere and compatible with standard PyTorch operations. Seeded experiments and the developed programmatic framework for differentiable multidimensional fairness losses are provided in the appendix.

Datasets

We experiment on the Adult (Dua, Graff et al. 2017), Bank (Moro, Cortez, and Rita 2014), and Compas (Angwin et al. 2022) datasets commonly used for demonstrating bias mitigation algorithms. From the public versions we work with, Adult contains 32,561 samples spanning 14 features, and binary label indicates whether income is above 50K. We consider gender as the sensitive attribute. The Bank dataset comprises 45,221 samples with 20 features, and a binary label indicating whether a client has subscribed to a term deposit. We consider the marital status (married, single, or divorced) as a sensitive attribute. We select a subset of the COMPAS dataset with X samples that focuses on Black and Caucasian defendants without missing values and a binary label indicating whether they re-offended within two years. We load 5 features frequently used features (age, gender, race, priors count, charge degree), with race being sensitive. Our framework accepts multiple sensitive attributes, values, and objects, but we avoid this complexity in experiments to preemptively avoid unforeseen challenges.

Selecting a definition

We avoid blind reuse of the previous section’s definitions and reverse engineer the popular 80%-rule often applied to our datasets, namely $prule \geq 0.8$ between men and women (Biddle 2017). Ratio-based discrimination matches Product of the three base logics; letting m, m' be the pr for men and women respectively, we get $e = 1 - prule$ in this logic and seek a restriction such that $e \leq 0.2$ yields $bias = 0$.

One restriction option is $g(s, e) = \{1 \text{ if } e \geq 0.2 \text{ else } 0\}$. Set predicate Tol with truth value $\mu(Tol) = 0.2$ and see that $g(s, e)$ can obtain binary truth values if it is the truth value of a strong negation. Furthermore, 0 can be obtained in Product logic only if logical implication is involved. Thus rewrite:

$$g(s, e) = ((1 - (\mu(Tol) \Rightarrow e)) \Rightarrow 0) = \{1 \text{ if } e \geq 0.2 \text{ else } 0\}$$

where $\dots \Rightarrow 0$ is strong negation. Substitute mathematical symbols with logic connectives whose truth values they represent (e.g., \Rightarrow with \rightarrow) to obtain the generating restriction:

$$G(S, E) \triangleq \overset{strwk}{\neg \neg} (Tol \rightarrow E)$$

What Tol represents may change with the context. We set our motivation as a starting point of discussion: $Tol \triangleq \text{acceptable numerical deviation from target truth values}$.

Even this simple underlying definition covers many popular practices: it is already derived from disparate impact/demographic parity, and can model equal opportunity relaxations by creating a threshold in Lukasiewicz logic and setting $m = tpr$. It can similarly model the more general equalized odds by also accounting for tnr for each group - consider a second variation of the group equipped with a different fairness concern. But the definition also supports new configurations, and not merely those already explored.

Since in all datasets mitigating tpr disparities is far more challenging than those of tnr or pr , we focus only on mitigating those. We set the truth value $\mu(Tol)$ as an adjustable choice with values in $\{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$. All experiments consider group members to be eventually encountered, that is, $s = 1$.

Results

Table 2 shows the average (*mean*) and standard deviation (*std*) of the proportions of models achieving perfect fairness (*ppf*). We also report overall *acc* and *tpr*, which are directly affected by changes to the loss too. Finally, we look at the proportion of models satisfying notions of equal opportunity (*eo*); this differs from *ppf* only in fixing the BL subclass to Lukasiewicz logic during evaluation. The variation of *ppf* being greater than other measures indicates heterogeneous fairness assessment that reflects opinion differences.

All measures fluctuate by more than 15% *std* relative to *mean*, indicating that the logic type and $\mu(Tol)$ choices affecting bias—and ultimately the loss—have a tangible impact on trained models. Furthermore, *ppf* has the largest *std*, both comparatively and in absolute terms. As this quantity also depends on the definition of fairness employed during evaluation, the increased deviation demonstrates that stakeholder choices influence not only training but also model assessment and selection. By exhibiting larger *std* than that of *eo* we verify that the logic subclass matters too.

For example, two groups with *tpr* values (0.5, 0.8) perfectly satisfy the selected fairness for $\mu(Tol) = 0.4$ in Product but not Lukasiewicz logic. Whereas (0.22, 0.4) are perfectly fair for the same $\mu(Tol)$ in Lukasiewicz but not Product logic. Find computations in the appendix.

	Adult		Bank		Compas	
	<i>mean</i>	<i>std</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>std</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>std</i>
<i>acc</i>	0.757	0.129	0.674	0.325	0.557	0.086
<i>tpr</i>	0.665	0.236	0.514	0.342	0.657	0.340
<i>eo</i>	0.787	0.291	0.904	0.176	0.422	0.311
<i>ppf</i>	0.665	0.377	0.689	0.400	0.412	0.339

Table 2: Comparison of *acc*, *tpr*, *ep*, *ppf* across datasets. Deviations corresponding to the largest coefficient of variation $\frac{std}{mean}$ are in **bold**.

6 Conclusions

In this paper we introduced the concept of expressing fairness definitions in Basic fuzzy Logic (BL) to make domain expert assumptions and free choices explicit. We presented common assumptions in the logic, and used these to arrive at a standardized framework of what numerical fairness definitions look like. We showed how the framework can be used in practice to explain and adjust definitions in new application contexts, and experimented on real datasets, where free choices to be filled by stakeholders alter evaluation outcomes.

Future works—including regulatory efforts—can use our transparent modeling instead of heuristic justification of algorithmic fairness definitions, especially if the goal is to involve non-technical people in the creation of context-specific definitions. They could also explain more advanced assumptions using BL, such as aggregate curve comparisons in measures like abroca (Gardner, Brooks, and Baker 2019).

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Appendix

In this appendix we present aspects of the case study and deterministic computations that we skipped in the main paper in favor of concise presentation. We also provide an indicative segment of intermediate *ppf* results, before these are aggregated into an average and standard deviation.

Case study restriction

Here we describe the case study's design of a bias restriction. The design starts from the interdisciplinarily-selected question of the main text, summarized to *Q*: *If you could choose, would you prioritize non-discrimination or correctness?* A different statement and different interpretations could arise when applying our methodology elsewhere, even given the same question; this work's case study only exemplifies what evaluate systems in specific application contexts looks like.

Of the question's term, *discrimination* E is already part of our modeling. We consider non-discrimination and Q 's statement about correctness *Correct*, to be quantified through weak negation of discrimination and loss of business benefits *Err* counterparts. That is, non-discrimination and correctness obtain truth values $1 - \mu(E)$ and $\mu(\text{Correct}) = 1 - \mu(\text{Err})$ respectively.

Consider a scenario where we are certain, that is, require with truth value 1, that non-discrimination is more important than correctness when thinking of a fair system. In this case, the former should have greater truth value than the latter. That is: $1 - \mu(E) \geq \mu(\text{Correct})$. Since we aim to uncover a bias restriction, we require the opposite to indicate bias: $1 - \mu(E) \leq \mu(\text{Correct})$. Thus, the restriction should yield truth value 1 when $\mu(\text{Err}) \leq e$ which by definition is equivalent to $\mu(\text{Err}) \Rightarrow e$ with underlying BL statement $\text{Err} \rightarrow E$.³

We would then like to create a BL definition that relaxes the $\text{Err} \rightarrow E$ statement's truth value to allow some leeway. How much leeway is added is intuitively an implication from another predicate *Tol*. This leads to restriction candidate:

$$H(S, E) = \text{Tol} \rightarrow (E \rightarrow \text{Err})$$

³To keep explanations simple, we do not consider the opposite, namely looking at the truth value of violating $E \rightarrow \text{Err}$ if correctness is deemed more important. This could have been added to the chosen restriction in a way that reduces our evaluation to the truth value of the chosen formula when non-discrimination is more important but also allow an alternative when not.

We interpret Tol as a *bias intolerance* statement based on the intuition that its truth value interpolates between 1 yielding worst-case bias intolerance when $E \rightarrow Err$, and 0 that does not consider bias at any situation.

Unfortunately, in Product and Gödel logics $H(S, E)$ does not obtain zero truth value almost everywhere; it obtains zero truth value only for specific values (not ranges) of e . Therefore, it does not meet our empirical requirements of recognizing perfect fairness in realistic scenarios. We devise the following trick to instead snap its truth values to binary options $\{0, 1\}$ by mingling strong and weak negation:

$$G(S, E) = \overset{strwk}{\neg} \neg H(S, E)$$

Numerically, in the aforementioned two logics:

$$\mu(\overset{strwk}{\neg} \neg H) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(H) = 1, 0 \text{ otherwise}\}$$

In terms of interpreting the double negation of two different types, we suggest $G(S, E) \triangleq$ *do not disagree that the statement $H(S, E)$ holds*, where *do not* arises from the concept of mutual exclusiveness and *disagree* captures the more mild nature of weak negation.

Processing Case Study Feedback

Data processing. To select the type of logic preferred across 48 stakeholder replies, we compute the Nemenyi ranks, that is, the average across rank 1 for highest preference, 2 for second highest, etc. The preferred type of base measure used for computing ideally indistinguishable quantities m, m' is chosen according to a process (Demšar 2006) that runs a Friedman test at 0.01 p-value to verify the existence of statistically significant preferences followed by a post-hoc Nemenyi test at 0.05 p-value (the latter is larger because this test is typically weaker than alternatives).

Figure 3 summarizes feedback. Groups of the most preferred measures with statistically significant differences to the rest are circled. Due to no clear preference between the types of logic we adopted Gödel as the strongest—and most preferred—option. Finally, $\mu(Tol) = 0.06$ and, after asking system owners, we selected the loss of business benefits as $\mu(E) = 1 - acc$ for loan approval and $\mu(E) = 1 - tnr$ for face verification, both computed over the total population.

We aim to demonstrate our approach rather than gather social insights, but a finding that merits further investigation is that that mitigating pr disparities had lowest priority in these situations, despite being commonly studied.

Perfect fairness formula. Lastly, we show how fairness criteria are extracted by computing the range of the truth values of discrimination for which $fair = 1$. Given that we operate in Gödel logic, $bias = \min\{s, e, g(s, e)\}$. For $s, e \neq 0$ we obtain $bias = 0$ only if $g(s, e) = 0$. That is:

$$1 \neq h(s, e)$$

where $h(s, e) = \mu(H(s, e)) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Tol) \leq \mu(Err \rightarrow E), \mu(Err \rightarrow E) \text{ otherwise}\}$. Also $\mu(Err \rightarrow E) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Err) \leq e, e \text{ otherwise}\}$. We now obtain:

- if $\mu(Err) \leq e$ and $\mu(Tol) \leq e$ then $h(s, e) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Tol) \leq e, e \text{ otherwise}\} = 1$

Figure 3: 48 replies summarized as Nemenyi ranks for group assessment on loan approval (upper left—prefer lower) and face verification (upper right), preference percentages for different logics (bottom left—prefer higher), and preference of business benefits (bottom right) as opposed to fairness.

- if $\mu(Err) \leq e$ and $\mu(Tol) > e$ then $h(s, e) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Tol) \leq 1, e \text{ otherwise}\} = e$
- if $\mu(Err) > e$ and $\mu(Tol) \leq e$ then $h(s, e) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Tol) \leq e, e \text{ otherwise}\} = e$
- if $\mu(Err) > e$ and $\mu(Tol) > e$ then $h(s, e) = \{1 \text{ if } \mu(Tol) \leq 1, e \text{ otherwise}\} = 1$

Perfect fairness can hence be achieved only if $e \neq 1$ and either $\mu(Err) \leq e < \mu(Tol)$ or $\mu(Tol) \leq e < \mu(Err)$. Consider two cases:

- if $\mu(Err) \leq \mu(Tol)$ then only the first condition holds
- if $\mu(Err) > \mu(Tol)$ then only the second holds

Therefore, perfect fairness is obtained only if:

$$\min\{\mu(Tol), \mu(Err)\} \leq e < \max\{\mu(Tol), \mu(Err)\}$$

The requisite $e \neq 1$ is satisfied by this definition, as the truth value of discrimination becomes smaller than another truth value that can at most be 1.

Lastly, we substitute specific quantities for the loan approval system, where stakeholder opinions are processed into $\mu(Err) = 0.06$ and $e = 1 - \min_i tpr$ across all groups i based on the truth values of discrimination computed in base logics (see next section) across pairs of groups. Business owners consider the overall system accuracy as correctness $\mu(Correct) = acc$, meaning that $\mu(Err) = 1 - acc$.

Hence, fairness with truth value 1 is obtained only if:

$$\min\{0.06, 1 - acc\} \leq 1 - \min_i tpr < \max\{0.06, 1 - acc\}$$

and equivalently, if at least one group has tpr less than 0.94

$$\min\{0.94, acc\} < \min_i tpr \leq \max\{0.94, acc\}$$

For the face verification system we similarly obtain:

$$\min\{0.94, tnr\} < \min_i acc \leq \max\{0.94, tnr\}$$

$$\min\{0.94, tnr\} < \min_i tpr \leq \max\{0.94, tnr\}$$

$$\min\{0.94, tnr\} < \min_i tnr \leq \max\{0.94, tnr\}$$

Our family of fairness definitions ends up considering systems fair only if at least one group underperforms. This counter-intuitive proposition could be interpreted as our restriction shedding doubt about its own suitability for systems where all groups are high-performing. If such doubt is not needed, it can also be eliminated by further restrictions (to be conjuncted on the one we employ).

Discrimination under base BL subclasses

Here, we compute the truth value of the discrimination definition $\overset{wk}{\neg}(M \leftrightarrow M')$ for the three base BL subclasses, namely Gödel, Product, and Lukasiewicz logic. We do so by substituting the t-norm connectives of those logics with their truth value computations. We annotate $m = \mu(M)$, $m' = \mu(M')$ and use $\overset{wk}{\sim}$ to annotate the truth value of $\overset{wk}{\neg}$.

Gödel logic discrimination

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(E) &= \overset{wk}{\sim} ((m \Rightarrow m') \star (m' \Rightarrow m)) \\ &= 1 - \min\{\{1 \text{ if } m \leq m', m' \text{ otherwise}\}, \\ &\quad \{1 \text{ if } m' \leq m, m \text{ otherwise}\}\} \\ &= 1 - \min\{m', m\} \end{aligned}$$

Product logic discrimination

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(E) &= \overset{wk}{\sim} ((m \Rightarrow m') \star (m' \Rightarrow m)) \\ &= 1 - \min\{(1 \text{ if } m \leq m', \frac{m'}{m} \text{ otherwise}), \\ &\quad (1 \text{ if } m' \leq m, \frac{m}{m'} \text{ otherwise})\} \\ &= 1 - \min\{\min\{1, \frac{m}{m'}\}, \min\{1, \frac{m'}{m}\}\} \\ &= 1 - \min\{\frac{m}{m'}, \frac{m'}{m}\} \\ &= 1 - \frac{\min\{m', m\}}{\max\{m', m\}} \end{aligned}$$

The above holds when $\min\{m, m'\} \neq 0$. For $m = m' = 0$ we obtain $\mu(E) = \overset{wk}{\sim} ((0 \Rightarrow 0) \star (0 \Rightarrow 0)) = 1 - (1 \star 1) = 0$. For $m' = 0 \neq m$ without loss of generality we obtain $\mu(E) = \overset{wk}{\sim} ((0 \Rightarrow m) \star (m \Rightarrow 0)) = 1 - (1 \cdot \frac{0}{m}) = 1$.

Lukasiewicz logic discrimination

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(E) &= \overset{wk}{\sim} ((m \Rightarrow m') \star (m' \Rightarrow m)) \\ &= 1 - \min\{\min\{1, 1 - m + m'\}, \min\{1, 1 - m' + m\}\} \\ &= 1 - \min\{1 - m + m', 1 - m' + m\} \\ &= \max\{-m + m', -m' + m\} = |m - m'| \end{aligned}$$

Example on definition disagreement

Consider the last example of Section 5, where tpr values can be either (0.5, 0.8) (case i) or (0.22, 0.4) (case ii) and $\mu(Tol) = 0.4$ under fairness definition with restriction $G(S, E) \triangleq \overset{strwk}{\neg} \overset{strwk}{\neg} (Tol \rightarrow E)$. In Product logic:

$$bias = s \cdot e \cdot g(s, e) = s \cdot e \cdot \{1 \text{ if } e \geq 0.2, 0 \text{ otherwise}\}$$

which means that $fair = 1$ only if $e < 2$. The same holds true for Gödel logic. In Lukasiewicz logic for $s = 1$ and given that in that logic $\overset{strwk}{\neg} \overset{strwk}{\neg} X = X$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} bias &= \max\{e + \min\{1 - \mu(Tol) + e, 1\} - 1, 0\} \\ &= \max\{2e - \mu(Tol), 0\} \end{aligned}$$

and therefore $fair = 1$ only if $e \leq \frac{\mu(Tol)}{2}$. These helper definitions are also used by our implementation. We now check these conditions numerically.

- Product logic and case i:
 $e = 1 - \frac{0.5}{0.8} = 0.375 < 0.4$ and therefore $fair = 1$
- Lukasiewicz and case i:
 $e = |0.5 - 0.8| = 0.3 > \frac{0.4}{2}$ and therefore $fair \neq 1$
- Product logic and case ii:
 $e = 1 - \frac{0.22}{0.4} = 0.45 \geq 0.4$ and therefore $fair \neq 1$
- Lukasiewicz and case ii:
 $e = |0.22 - 0.4| = 0.18 \leq \frac{0.4}{2}$ and therefore $fair = 1$

Subset of experiment details

As a last segment to this appendix, in Table 3 we provide a glimpse into some of the intermediate values gathered during experimentation. These demonstrate how important the choice of logic and parameters is in the training and test fairness definitions, which in turn shows that stakeholder-backed choices can be meaningful.

$\mu(Tol)$	Evaluation logic		
	Gödel	Product	Lukasiewicz
Trained with Gödel logic loss with $\mu(Tol) = 0.1$			
0.1	97	99	96
0.2	100	100	99
0.3	100	100	100
0.4	100	100	100
0.5	100	100	100
Trained with Product logic loss with $\mu(Tol) = 0.1$			
0.1	0	61	95
0.2	0	71	100
0.3	0	83	100
0.4	0	88	100
0.5	0	91	100
Trained with Lukasiewicz loss with $\mu(Tol) = 0.1$			
0.1	10	31	54
0.2	10	68	94
0.3	10	94	100
0.4	20	96	100
0.5	12	99	100

Table 3: How many out of 100 models perfectly achieved fairness per the bias restriction of experiments given stakeholder choices and the Bank dataset.

Our experiments span only one BL definition that is a direct modeling of common principles. The table is also restricted to one dataset and one training tolerance. However, it is already apparent that different training and evaluation methodologies create a substantial difference of how often systems are considered fair.

Furthermore, the training loss influences the test assessment based on strictness, where Gödel logic is more strict than the others and hence training to satisfy its fairness often creates perfect fairness for other logics. This could come at the cost of accuracy, but such investigation lies outside the scope of this work. For future work, we point to ordering several BL subclasses in terms of strictness.